

Politics of Ethnic Identity: Koch Rajbanshi of Assam

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Abstract: *This article explores the unfolding of identity politics within the Koch-Rajbanshi community of Assam, examining how the stress between the inner self and social recognition leads to ethnic and political mobilisation. The concept of identity has shifted from being personal to a collective demand for social recognition, the Koch-Rajbanshi community in Assam is a compelling case in this. The article specifically focuses on the Koch Rajbanshi community, highlighting their efforts to establish a distinct identity within Assamese society and their aspirations for recognition as a scheduled tribe. Led by the nascent middle class, this movement emphasises the politics of difference, to challenge the socio-economic marginalisation and assert their status as sons of the soil. It concludes by noting the relevance of social identity theory in understanding group dynamics and social change.*

Keywords: *Identity, Identity Politics, Koch-Rajbanshi, Kshatriyization, Assamization.*

Introduction

The terms 'identity and identity politics' have been popularized by psychologist Erik Erikson in the 1950s. Today, identity has a wide range of connotations, referring to social categories or roles in some circumstances, and basic facts about oneself in others. The distinction between one's genuine inner self and an exterior world of social laws and norms that do not fully respect that inner self's worth or dignity is where identity begins. Individuals have always felt out of place in cultures throughout history (Fukuyama 2018).

However, it is only recently that the idea has gained traction that the real inner self is fundamentally important and that the outer society is habitually incorrect and unfair in its assessment of the former. It is not the inner self that must be forced to follow society's rules, but society itself that must change. The inner feeling of dignity yearns for acknowledgment. It is insufficient for one to have a sense of his or her worth if others do not openly recognize it, or worse, if they degrade or deny their existence (Fukuyama 2018).

The latter half of the 20th century witnessed the rise of significant political movements, including second-wave feminism, the Black Civil Rights movement in the United States, the gay and lesbian liberation movement, and the American Indian Movement. These movements were characterized by their focus on addressing perceived injustices inflicted upon specific social groups. Supporting these social movements was a philosophical literature that delved into the essence, origins, and potential futures of the identities being advocated for. Identity politics, as a method of organizing, is closely intertwined with the belief that certain social groups face oppression. It argues that one's identity, such as being a woman or an African American, exposes individuals to various forms of cultural imperialism, violence, exploitation, marginalization, or powerlessness. Identity politics begins by analyzing these types of social injustices and proposes different approaches, such as reclaiming, redefining, or transforming previously stigmatized notions of a group membership. Instead of accepting the negative narratives imposed by a dominant culture regarding one's supposed inferiority, individuals strive to reshape their self-perception and foster a stronger sense of community (Heyes 2020).

The modern sense of identity swiftly turns into identity politics, in which individuals demand public affirmation of their worth since humans crave attention.

As a result, identity politics comprises a major portion of today's political struggle, from democratic revolutions to new social movements. When it comes to ethnicity or ethnic identity, there are two major perspectives to consider: primordial and instrumental. According to the primordialists, ethnic identity can be determined at birth, based on a person's sense of belonging in his or her community, religion, language, and cultural traditions. For the instrumental version, Ethnic identity is socially formed and the result of one's deliberate choice; elites play a significant role in this process, as they employ symbols such as language, ethnicity, and culture as markers (Brass 1991).

The establishment of ethnic identity begins with economic, political, and cultural rivalry and struggle among the community's leaders and other ethnic groups. One's dignity is tied to one's identity, so identity politics breeds divisions and fury over injustices done to them rather than on resemblance, likeness, and connection within their group or community. When ethnic grievances and frustrations threaten the ethnic identity and the ethnic masses become aware of it through the influence of print media, pamphlets, and other informal means, fear and discontent lead to conflict. The Rajbanshi of Assam are examples of this.

Who are these Koch Rajbanshis?

They are a South Asian ethnic group found in Nepal, Bhutan, Bangladesh, and India. They are found in abundance in Indian states such as Assam, Meghalaya, North Bengal, and a portion of Bihar. As a geographical region, the natural boundaries run from the Tista Brahmaputra valley in the east to the Tista Kortoya in the west, encompassing regions such as Jalpaiguri, Cooch Behar, and the southern part of Darjeeling district in West Bengal, as well as parts of Dinajpur and Rangpur districts in Bangladesh, and Kokrajhar, Bongaigaon, Dhubri, Goalpara, Barpeta, Bijni, Kamrup, and (Barman 2007:13). The Rajbanshis, also called Koches in some areas, are the major residents of these areas, consequently, the terms Koch and Rajbanshis are used interchangeably here. According to colonial ethnographers, Rajbanshis were a purified version of the Koch who had abandoned the conventional social system and conventions. In North Bengal, indigenous writers such as Upendranath Brama, Hari Kishore Barman, and others considered that Rajbanshis were superior to Kochs, but in Assam, due to circumstantial elements that will be detailed here, the terms are used equally.

Overt cultural form is defined as the same group of people exhibiting different behavioral patterns when confronted with different circumstances, opportunities, and environments (Barth:1969). This can be seen among the Rajbanshis of North Bengal and Assam, where each group exhibits differences in their behavior due to a geographical divide and a different cultural milieu at play. Despite having a common ancestor, the Rajbanshi of the northern part of Bengal regard Assam as distinct from them, and vice versa.

Through geographical restructuring, the barrier that divides Assam and Bengal has harmed language, cultural homogeneity, demographic structure, and community solidarity. According to Ananda Gopal Ghosh, the main cause leading to the continuous marginalization of the community have four dimensions, the Bengali side, the colonial-imperial side, the Assamese side, and the Rajbanshi side, and finally, the subdivision into the Assamese Rajbanshi and The Bengali Rajbanshi (Ghosh 2007:94). The Rajbanshi leaders did not realize where they were heading, as in Assam there had been no such demand for mother tongue, also the division between Assam and Bengal laid to the loss of the twenty decades relation-

ship. The process of Assamization in Assam and Bengalization in Bengal formed a permanent rift between the Rajbanshis of Assam and North Bengal.

The fundamental cause of the community's continued marginalization, according to Ananda Gopal Ghosh, has four dimensions: the Bengali side, the colonial-imperial side, the Assamese side, and the Rajbanshi side, with the split into the Assamese Rajbanshi and the Bengali Rajbanshi (Ghosh 2007:94). The Rajbanshi leaders were unaware of their fate, as there had been no such demand for their mother tongue in Assam, and the divide between Assam and Bengal had resulted in the loss of a twenty-year relationship. Assamization and Bengalization in Assam and Bengal, respectively, created a lasting schism between the Rajbanshis of Assam and North Bengal.

The Assamese have benefited greatly from the foundation of the area, with language serving as the primary medium of teaching in Assam. The Rajbanshi's identity was harmed by cultural dominance, as they lost their identity as a community during the Bengalese-Assamese battle. (Ghosh 2007:101). During the Bengalese-Assamese conflict, Rajbanshis sided with the Assamese, and young educated Rajbanshis such as Sarat Chandra Sinha, Raja Ajit Narayan Das, Puhendu Narayan Sinha, and others called for Rajbanshi assimilation with the Assamese. Since 1920, the Assamese script has been used by the Rajbanshis of Assam to write Rajbanshi literature, whereas the Rajbanshis of Bengal used the Bengali script because Rajbanshi had no distinct script. While the Koch-Rajbanshis were striving for tribal identity in Assam, there was a movement for kshatriya status in the northern region of West Bengal led by Panchanan Barma. Hence, an ideological divide arose that is still unbridgeable. Ghosh states that the Rajbanshis of North Bengal and Assam had a remarkable chance to reunify under the State-Reorganisation Commission in 1953 following independence, but were unable to do so.

Goalpara's Koch-Rajbanshis wanted to be part of Assam, consequently young leaders like Sree Sarat Chandra Sinha of the Goalpara district and Muslim migrants led by Muhammad Omaruddin had put together a huge protest against Goalpara's admission to West Bengal (Ghosh 2021:14). While the Koch Rajbanshis of Assam were still contesting for the Schedule Tribe Status, the Rajbanshis in Bengal who identify themselves as Kshatriyas are contended with Schedule Caste status under the Indian constitution with all the benefits and concessions.

Politics of Identity and Autonomy in Assam.

In the pre-colonial era, the social life of the North East India's Ethnic groups was confined to their families, clans, and hamlets, and they remained isolated. The consciousness of one's ethnic identity grew when they suffered the loss of it, which eventually led to many ethno-political movements in the North East of India. The policies of the colonial administrator regarding land and forest led to alienation of land, adding to it the wealthy immigrants becoming the owners of the land, non-tribal immigration, low socio-economic development, lack of modern communication in the regions. Led to a feeling of discontentment, alienation led to various social movements.

In Assam, plain tribes like the Bodos started demanding the Bodo language as a medium of instruction in higher secondary schools and also the implementation of the Fifth Schedule in the tribal belt districts of Assam, like Kamrup, Goalpara, North Lakhimpur, and Darrang. Also, the formation of the Bodo autonomous council, according to Niru Hazarika, accelerated the demand for autonomy. This

led to the rise of consciousness among many other ethnic groups like Ahom, Rabha, and Koch Rajbanshis, who also started claiming their indigenous rights and identities, leading to inter-ethnic fear and prejudices similar to the predatory identity as mentioned by Appadurai (2006) in, *Fear of Small Numbers*". Even the Koch-Rajbanshis of Assam started their identity movement, demanding greater autonomy, scheduled tribe status, which includes land rights and greater autonomy over their territory.

There was nothing like Assamese till a few centuries ago. According to Nandana Dutta, before that, it was Bodo, Dimasa, Karbi, Koch, Ahom, Tiwa, Mising, Sonowal, Moran, Motok, Chutiya, Bamun, Sudhir, Kayastha, Kalita, and so on. The term "Ahom" became "Assam" during the colonial period. While many tribal languages with dialects such as Kamtapuri, Goalpari, and Darang were recognized as Assamese languages during the standardization process, it was a narrower view of identity development. Assam was now for Assamese-speaking people, and those who didn't speak the same language were considered second-class citizens (Dutta 2012:193). Muga silk, Mekhla chador, red and white Gamosa, traditional conical hat Japi, and offering tray Xorai are all part of Assamese culture. Indigenous tribe cultures were overlooked, such as the Dokana, a traditional Bodo women's dress, and the Koch tribe's Lipan and Patani. The tribe's unique culture and clothing were ignored.

The All-Bodo Students Union and Bodo People's Action Committee signed the Bodo accord in February 2003. Eventually, the Bodo Autonomous Council was formed. According to the law, any village having a population of more than 50 percent Bodo will be under the Bodo Autonomous Council. After the Bodoland Territorial Act was passed and under the 6th Schedule, consisting of four districts, Kokrajhar, Chirang, Udalguri, and Baksa, collectively formed the Bodoland Territorial Autonomous Districts (Haloi 2018:74), the success of the Bodo in Assam opened the minds of Rajbanshi leaders and intellectuals in Assam. They realized that Bodo had the fundamental right in the BTAD area with only a five percent majority, whereas Koch Rajbanshis have a majority of about seventy-five percent, along with the other non-Bodo (Haloi 2018:94). Koch-Rajbanshi, however, realized the Bodo were in an advantageous position in terms of Government jobs and other facilities like land rights. Intellectuals and leaders of the Rajbanshi community in Assam began to try to establish their own cultural identity, which means a steady process of disassociation from the Assamese. They attempted to distance themselves from the Kshatriya Rajbanshi identity by referring to themselves as Koch-Rajbanshi rather than just Rajbanshi. Like the other mongoloid lineages, they began to demand scheduled tribe status.

Despite their best efforts, they were unable to carve out a niche for themselves in Assamese society. They understood they needed political authority, so they began "bargaining for political power-sharing." These compelled them to create their political border, and identity and autonomy began to emerge under the leadership of the community's middle class. Unlike hill tribes such as the Nagas, Mizos, Khasis, Garos, Dimasa, and Karbi, whose autonomy movement was primarily political, the plain tribe movement primarily focused on the primordial aspect of protecting and preserving their language, culture, tradition, and script, gradually separating themselves from Assamese identity and demanding their political identity.

In North-East India, individuals of Mongoloid descent are classified as a

Scheduled Tribe, however, the Rajbanshis, who prefer to be called Koch-Rajbanshi in Assam, have not been included in the Scheduled Tribe list, while they hold Scheduled Caste status in North Bengal. In Assam, their expression of ethnic identity has not mirrored that of groups like the Nagas and Mizo. In the past thirty years, they have shown limited awareness of their identity and have not actively taken to the streets to advocate for their rights. Compared to other tribes, the Koch-Rajbanshi community is relatively less advanced in education and economic development. It has been noted that more developed tribes, such as the Naga, demand recognition akin to a sovereign state. In contrast, relatively less developed tribes tend to assert regional autonomy, while those that are even less developed, like the Koch-Rajbanshis, often seek special protection, appearing less assertive and more docile (Dutta 1990:163).

As the Rajbanshis of Bengal were listed as Schedule caste so the Koch-Rajbanshis should be included in the list as Schedule Caste was a former argument but Meghalaya which emerged as a fully-fledged State and the Meghalaya State Assembly budget session in 1980 adopted a resolution requesting the Government of India to recognize the Koch people of the State as a tribe and include them in the relevant list (Dutta 1990:166), the Koch-Rajbanshi of Assam realized that there is a need to reconstruct their demand to be included in the Schedule tribe list. If Koch in Meghalaya is getting Schedule Tribe status, then they should also. Union minister of social welfare, Sitaram Kesari, had suggested dropping the Kshatriya identity to strengthen their demand for ST status (Prodhani 2015), as the Kshatriya identity was a Hindu one and goes against the demand for tribal identity. Thereby, the community started following certain actions and behavioral patterns, which will help them demand Schedule Tribe status. They are trying to incorporate them into their daily life. The revival of the culture, language, and food, along with the reconfiguration of the practices, which are considered integral, and also some practices are abandoned to make space for the new objectives. They want to forget the memories of the Kshatriya movement and cling to the memory of the past, which will help them acquire Scheduled Tribe status.

The Rajbanshi community, in accordance with the socio-political environment, has been readjusting its identity boundary accordingly, with newer challenges and turn of events, they are reshaping their collective memory. Retrieving traditional costumes, reshaping social traditions like using the *yellow gamocha*, proliferation of literature in the mother tongue, and relocating the almost lost sites of mythic and historical significance (Prodhani 2014:19). Assamese discriminated against the Koch-Rajbanshis and were never considered in terms of socio-cultural and linguistic practices. With the process of Assamisation, the middle class among the Koch-Rajbanshis is more conscious of their identity than the common masses. "So, they are trying to bring back their distinctiveness in culture, language, and modern civilization, as they are the son of the soil" (Prodhani 2014).

It is also observed that in Assam, Koch-Rajbanshis are seeking to disassociate themselves from the Rajbanshi label. The name Rajbanshi bears a distinct Kshatriya identity; many interviewees, during interaction, insisted on being called or identified as Koch rather than Rajbanshi. To assert this Koch identity, several have adopted 'Koch' as their surname. For instance, one interviewee's formal name is Madan Roy, but on social media uses the name Jajang Kama Koch. When enquired about it, he explained the word 'Jajang' is a Koch word commonly used in Meghalaya, noting that the Koch people historically followed a clan-based system

where the last name was according to one's specific clan.¹

For the Koch-Rajbanshis, it is difficult to disown the "Rajbanshi" name entirely. Colonial ethnographers and scholars view the Rajbanshis as the purified form of the Koch, those who have adopted Hindu customs, while "Koch" was classified as a tribal identity. Ironically, those who identify themselves as Koch consider themselves superior to those of Rajbanshis. In Upper Assam, specifically within the Sonitpur and Nagaon districts, the Koches never called themselves Rajbanshis; they are simply Koch. Furthermore, the Koch community in Upper Assam differs considerably from those of the Gaolpara, Dhubri, Kokrajhar, and Bongaigaon Districts, in respect of their material culture.²

Kankan Roy, the Kokrajhar district president of All Koch-Rajbanshi Students' Union, asserts that there is no distinct *jati* called "Rajbanshi"; rather, the term was popularized by Panchanan Barma, the social reformer. Roy further states that in Bengal, the Koch were historically termed as uncultured and uncivilized, labeled with derogatory terms like *Bahe Jati*. While Panchanan Barma tried to distinguish the Koch from the Rajbanshis, to achieve social mobility, Roy maintains that "Koch-Rajbanshi" is not a separate ethnic entity. He notes that in some districts of lower Assam, such as Bongaigaon and Kokrajhar, Koch-Rajbanshis as a community were heavily influenced by the Kshatriya movement. He contends that one cannot leave the Koch identity, as it represents the predominant "root" of the collective memory.³

During fieldwork in Kokrajhar, I observed the emergence of newer organizations like Koch Literary and Cultural Forum, working in collaboration with All Koch-Rajbanshis Students' Union (AKRSU). These groups are actively trying to revive the Koch language. My findings suggest that the Koch-Rajbanshis of Assam are strategically aligning their cultural identity with the specific criteria required for the specification of 'Scheduled Areas' or 'Schedule Tribe' status. The reclaim of the Koch language in Assam, which was limited till Meghalaya, is a calculated political approach with the intention to fulfill the prerequisites of the institutional requirement for tribal recognition under the Indian Constitution.

As Barth Mentions, in a society with multiple ethnic groups, the cultural traits that distinguish each group are found in aspects of life that are not publicly expressed. These aspects are considered the "backstage" for minority groups, where cultural features that are stigmatized by the dominant culture can be openly discussed and traded. (Barth 1969:32)

Conclusion

To conclude, according to Mary Bernstein, one can say that social identity theory helps explain the cognitive and cultural processes involved in fostering group identities and how those translate into prejudices, conflict, and even violence. All explanations for the group behaviour and conflicts reflect some underlying psychological assumptions about how such identity is passively or actively constructed, which in turn influences accounts of intergroup behaviour and social change.

Endnotes

1. Jajang Kama Koch interviewed on 23rd July 2018 in Guwahati.
2. Report of the Assam Institute of Research for Tribal and Scheduled Castes, Jawahar Nagar, Khenapara, Guwahati, Assam – 781022.
3. Kankan Roy interviewed on 24th July 2018 in Kokrajhar.

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